

**ACORRELATIONAL STUDY BETWEEN TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS AND
ADJUSTMENT OF TEACHERS TEACHING VISUALLY IMPAIRED
CHILDREN WITH RESPECT TO PROFESSIONAL
QUALIFICATION.**

Dr. MugdhaSangelkar

Pal Rajendra B.Ed College, Mumbai-400101

“The Constitution of India ensures equality, freedom, justice and dignity of all individuals and implicitly mandates an inclusive society for all including persons with disabilities.”

---National Policy on Disability 2006

In the recent years, there have been vast and positive changes in the perceptions of the society towards persons with disabilities. It has been realized that a majority of persons with disabilities can lead a better quality of life if they have equal opportunities and effective access to education and rehabilitation measures.

Among various disabilities, visual impairment is perhaps one of the oldest categories identified for special education, perhaps because visual impairment is apparent and provokes strong emotions. In most of the countries special facilities and programmes for the visually challenged were established before those for other groups of disabled individuals.

The role of a teacher teaching visually impaired children assumes greater importance than being a parent of the child whose involvement with the child demands utmost care and extraordinary levels of patience. The role encompasses multifaceted skills to shape up the visually impaired child, to make it learn, all that the world expects from it even from the basic life skills like eating, dressing up etc. All such responsibilities can be met if the teacher is well adjusted in his life.

Title of the Study:

A study on the correlation between Teaching Effectiveness and Adjustment of Teachers teaching Visually Impaired Children with respect to Professional Qualification

Objective of the study:

To find out the difference in the correlation of teaching effectiveness and adjustment of teachers teaching visually impaired children of secondary schools with respect to Professional Qualification.

Hypothesis of the study:

There is no significant difference in the correlation between Teaching Effectiveness and Adjustment of teachers teaching visually impaired children with respect to Professional Qualification (Professional Training for Special Children/ only Professional Training).

Operational Definition of the Terms Used:-

Visually impaired students:

Operationally visually impaired children can be defined as “Students who have total absent of sight, partial absent of sight or low vision” or “those whose vision is so defective that they cannot be educated through visual methods and hence have to be educated through channels other than vision”.

1. Teaching Effectiveness:

2. ‘Teaching effectiveness’ is defined as the knowledge, skills and the attitude in a teacher’s repertoire for achieving the intended effects in the visually impaired children of secondary schools.

In the present study Teaching Effectiveness refers to scores obtained on Teaching Effectiveness Tool for Teachers Teaching Visually Impaired Children developed by the researcher.

Adjustment:

Lazarus explains, “The psychologist is more concerned with what might be called psychological survival or adjustment rather than psychological concept of adaptation as adjustment to demand”.

In the present study adjustment refers to scores obtained on Mangal Teacher Adjustment Inventory (MTAI Short Form) developed by S K Mangal.

Research Design and Methodology:

In the execution of the present study, descriptive survey method of research was employed.

Population:

The population in this study refers to all the teachers teaching visually impaired children at secondary schools in Mumbai city.

Sample:

Researcher investigated all the schools of Mumbai city of Maharashtra where visual impaired students are enrolled and are in secondary level i.e. studying in VIII, IX and X standard. Thus all the teachers teaching visually impaired children at secondary level of Mumbai city of Maharashtra are included in the sample. Only the teachers who had taken long leave like maternity leave, sick leave or any other leave during the collection of data were excluded from the sample.

Hence, total Sample for the present study is consisted of 118 teachers teaching visually impaired children at secondary level. 48 among them have qualified teacher training course for special children while 70 have qualified only teacher training course.

Sampling Technique:

The Sample technique used for the present study is “**Purposive Sampling**”.

Tools:

The instruments employed by the researcher for the present study were:

1. Researcher - developed Teaching Effectiveness Tool for Teachers Teaching Visually Impaired Children (TETTTVI) in English.
2. Standardized tool of S.K. Mangal’s Mangal Teacher Adjustment Inventory (MTAI Short Form) English.

Procedure of Collection of Data:

In the present investigation, the data has been collected from different regions of Mumbai. Firstly the researcher sought permission of the head of her department, then she approached the principals, coordinators of SSA, Director of NAB where visually impaired children are studying. After that the subjects (teachers) were approached and were explained the purpose of the present study. This way a good rapport was established with the teachers. Prior administering the tools the researcher cleared out the instructions and gave necessary guidelines regarding the patterns of response to be made in each tool. When it was sure that they have understood the mode of recording their responses, the researcher then asked them to fill in the required information. In this way total 118 data were collected.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA:**TESTING OF HYPOTHESES:**

There is no significant difference in the correlation between Teaching Effectiveness and Adjustment of secondary school teachers teaching visually impaired children.

Table : Shows difference in the correlation between Teaching Effectiveness and Adjustment of teachers teaching visually impaired children of secondary schools with respect to Professional Qualification (Professional Training for Special Children/ only Professional Training)

Variables	Category (Professional Qualification)	N	Pearson's Co-efficient Correlation 'r' value	z-value
Teaching Effectiveness and Adjustment	With Professional Training for Special Children	48	-0.369	2.58*
	With only Professional Training	70	0.109	

* significant at .05 level

Interpretation:

The Table shows that the correlation (Pearson's Co-efficient Correlation) between Teaching Effectiveness and Adjustment of teachers teaching visually impaired children of secondary schools having Professional Training for Special Children is -0.369 and having only Professional Training is 0.109. The z value of these correlations was 2.58, which is significant. Hence the null hypothesis, 'there is no significant difference in the correlation between Teaching Effectiveness and Adjustment of teachers teaching visually impaired children with respect to Professional Qualification' is not accepted. Therefore there exists significant difference in the correlation between Teaching Effectiveness and Adjustment of teachers teaching visually impaired children with respect to Professional Qualification i.e. teachers having professional qualification for special children and teachers having only professional qualification.

Major Findings:

There exists significant difference in the relationship between Teaching Effectiveness and Adjustment of teachers teaching visually impaired children of secondary schools with respect to Professional Qualification (Professional Training for Special Children /only Professional Training).

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